

STUDIES IN THIXOTROPIC GELATION OF THORIUM MOLYBDATE GELS.

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The viscosity of thorium molybdate gels, which are thixotropic, has been measured during the process of gel-formation using Scarpa's method. The effect of change of concentrations of thorium nitrate, potassium molybdate and hydrochloric acid, of temperature and of the addition of electrolytes and non-electrolytes has also been examined. It is found that the viscosity-time curves are not continuous but show well-marked changes of direction. This is the first instance of its kind observed during the process of gel-formation.

Although Seifriz, Schalek and Freundlich were attracted by the phenomenon of concentrated sols giving rise to gels which liquefy on shaking, Schalek and Szegvari (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 318) were the first to point out the significance of this phenomenon. Several investigators have since attempted to study thixotropic gelation from various points of view. The principal workers on the subject are Freundlich and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 102; *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1927, 53, 231; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 180, 469; *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 309; 45, 348) who investigated the thixotropic behaviour of gels of ferric and aluminium oxides and of bentonite suspensions under different conditions and also examined the effects of the addition of electrolytes and non-electrolytes to them. Hauser (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 57) and Deutsch (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 180, 161) studied the influence of the dimensions of the containing vessel on the thixotropy of gels, the latter stating that this effect is only apparent. Kallmann and Kreidl (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 159, 322) measured the dielectric constant of vanadium pentoxide sol and found that it was diminished by 6% when the gel was formed but Kistler (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 815) found no change in the dielectric constant of thixotropic sols before and after gelation. Heymann (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 462) carried out dilatometric investigations during the sol-gel transformation of ferric hydroxide and found that there was no change in volume. Marinesco (*Compt. rend.*, 1932, 194, 1824) studied the effects of ultrasonic waves on thixotropic gelation and found that the mechanical disturbances produced are due to interference of the direct and reflected waves.

It is evident that in these sol-gel transformations the total volume of the system remains the same and hence the average distance between the constituent particles does not alter. The development of rigidity in a

fluid sol or the mechanism of thixotropic gelation has been explained by various school of workers in different ways. Satya Prakash and Biswas (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 549) who investigated the thixotropic behaviour of the gels of molybdate, phosphate and arsenate of thorium have explained thixotropy on their 'hydration-agglomeration hypothesis of jellies. According to them the phenomenon of thixotropy cannot be explained on the view put forward by von Weimarn (*Rep. Imp. Ind. Res. Inst. Osaka*, 1921, 9, 1) that the jellies are formed by the release of highly developed supersaturation.

Ostwald (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 46, 263), Hauser (*J. Rheology*, 1931, 2, 5), Freundlich ("Kapillar Chemie," 1932, II, 624) and Kistler (*loc. cit.*) explain thixotropic gelation on the consideration that the particles in the gel are surrounded by thick rigid envelopes of orientated water molecules or "lyospheres" which are destroyed by shaking and reformed on allowing the gel to stand; the gel is rigid when the lyospheres are large enough to make contact with each other throughout the system. The only evidence adduced for this theory is the observation by means of an ultra-microscope that during gel formation the Brownian movement of the gelling particles slows down and eventually ceases.

An alternative theory of thixotropic gelation has been put forward by Russell and Rideal (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1936, A 154, 540) who have collected evidence in favour of the view that thixotropic gelation is due to orientated coagulation. According to this theory the ultimate particles of which the gel-forming material is composed are anisotropic or anisometric or both and the charge and the adsorbed water molecules, if any, are unequally distributed. Adhesion occurs when two particles approach each other at particular orientation and three dimensional net-work or honey-comb structure, depending upon the nature of the particles, consisting of regularly orientated entities spread throughout the system, is formed. Any stress, such as shaking, destroys the orientation and the structure is reformed when the stress is removed. These authors have examined their theory in respect of all the known facts regarding thixotropic gelation and have found that it offers a satisfactory explanation for all of them.

Thomas Graham first pointed out in 1864 that viscometer could be employed as a colloidoscope. In 1913 Ostwald (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, 9, 34) emphasised the use of viscosity as a property suitable for the study of changes in a colloidal system. In recent years increasing attention has been paid to the study of this property which has been utilised for investigating (i) the mechanism of coagulation of sols, (ii) the degree of hydration of the colloid particles and (iii) the changes which take place during gelation.

A study of the literature shows that very scanty data are available on the viscosity measurements of gel-forming mixtures which give rise to thixotropic gels. Miller (*J. Rheology*, 1932, 3, 163) has investigated the thixotropic properties of paints viscosimetrically and noticed that the maximum fluidity immediately after violent agitation changes too rapidly for measurement.

In this investigation the viscosity of thorium molybdate gel-forming mixtures is measured at different intervals during the process of gel-formation. These gels have been found to be thixotropic by Satya Prakash and Biswas (*loc. cit.*). The effect of change of concentrations of thorium nitrate, potassium molybdate and hydrochloric acid, of temperature and of the addition of electrolytes and non-electrolytes on the viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures has also been examined.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The capillary methods of measuring viscosity have often been criticised because different results are obtained with colloidal systems by using capillary tubes of different diameters. Thus viscosity values of such systems measured by capillary viscometers have lost their usual significance and are now considered to be only empirically indicating the progress of coagulation or gelation. The shape of the viscosity-time curves is again dependent on the number of readings taken in a given interval of time (*cf.* Mardles, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 18, 327).

Scarpa's method modified by Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1394) was employed for the determination of the viscosity. The dimensions of the viscometer were as follows :

Volume of the bulb	= 1.54 c.c.
Diameter of the capillary	= 1.264 mm.
Length of the capillary	= 6.42 cm.

The time t_1 required by the mixture to rise through the capillary tube between two fixed marks at constant pressure (14.5 cm. of water) and the time of fall at atmospheric pressure t_2 , were measured at different intervals during the process of gel-formation. These intervals (in minutes) were the mean of the time at which the mixture was made to rise and that at which it reached the lower mark while falling since mixing the gel-forming constituents. The viscosity η was calculated from the relation

$$\eta = K \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

in which the constant K was experimentally determined by using a 60% solution of sucrose, the viscosity of which at 35° is given as 0.2662 (International Critical Tables, V, p. 23).

All chemicals used were of Kahlbaum's or Merck's extra pure quality ; potassium molybdate was obtained from the British Drug Houses. These chemicals were used as supplied by the manufacturers without further purification.

10% Solution of potassium molybdate, 2*N*-HCl and thorium nitrate solution (12 g. in 250 c.c., thoria content 2.24%) were made in redistilled water and were used throughout the investigation.

Preparation of Gels.

5 C.c. of the solution of thorium nitrate were taken in one test-tube and in another were taken solutions of potassium molybdate and hydrochloric acid together with the requisite quantity of distilled water so that after mixing the contents of the two test-tubes the total volume of the mixture was 10 c.c. The two test-tubes, with their contents were first placed in a thermostat maintained at 35° until they attained the constant temperature. They were then mixed by transferring the contents of the second test-tube into the first and back again three times. This manner of mixing was followed every time throughout the investigation. The mixture was then introduced into the viscometer bottle and the readings were immediately taken.

The results obtained are shown graphically :

- Fig. 1. Effect of the addition of different amounts of potassium molybdate to the mixture containing 0.24 g. of thorium nitrate and 0.04*N*-HCl.
- Fig. 2. Effect of the addition of different amounts of thorium nitrate to the mixture containing 0.05 g. of potassium molybdate and 0.04*N*-HCl.
- Fig. 3. Effect of the addition of HCl of different concentrations to the mixture containing 0.24 g. of thorium nitrate and 0.05 g. of potassium molybdate.

These curves show that the viscosity of thorium molybdate gel-forming mixtures increases rapidly at first, then decreases and again increases and so on. Thus the variation in viscosity of these mixtures with time is not a continuous function but there are well marked changes in direction.

From measurements of refractivity Joshi and co-workers* have shown for the first time that the progress of slow coagulation of sols and emulsions is not time-continuous but zonal. They regard slow coagulation to be more complex than a simple continued micellar coalescence contemplated by Smoluchowski and ascribe the zonal effect, in part, to building and unbuilding of the micelles during coagulation.

This is the first instance of its kind observed during the process of the formation of gels. Considering the fact that thorium molybdate gel is thixotropic, it will yield to any slight mechanical treatment, such as the one involved in sucking the mixture through the capillary tube. There will be a breaking up of the structure of the gel occasionally and this will cause the observed discontinuities in the viscosity-time curves. It appears that the discontinuous viscosity-time curve is a characteristic of highly thixotropic gels. This viewpoint is confirmed by the viscosity measurements of ceric phosphate gel-forming mixtures. These gels were prepared by Desai (unpublished work) for the first time by mixing solutions of ceric nitrate and phosphoric acid and were found to be thixotropic. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 4. If the gel is not highly thixotropic, *i.e.* it requires large force for its structure to break up, the viscosity-time curve may be a continuous one as has actually been observed in the case of the thixotropic thorium phosphate gel (*cf.* Mehta, Prasad and Parmar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 128).

One remarkable feature of all the curves is that the initial increase in viscosity is continuous in all cases. The time corresponding to the first maximum viscosity is compared with the thixotropic time of set in the following table from which it will be seen that the thixotropic action comes into play only when the specific structures are beginning to form.

TABLE I.

Thorium nitrate = 0.24 g. HCl = 0.04N.

Potassium molybdate (in 10 c.c. of the mixtures)	0.03g.	0.04g.	0.05g.	0.06g.	0.07g.
Time of set	185'	100'	65'	45'	32'
Thixotropic time of set	80'	50'	15'	7'	5'
Time corresp. to 1st maximum	113'	48'	18'	8'	—

* *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 141, 309, 775; 1937, 18, 103; *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1935, 4, 140; *Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 78, 145; *Fettchem. Umsch.*, 1936, 3, 36. "viscosity" *J. India Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329, 599, 699; 1934, 11, 133, 555, 573, 797; *J. chim. phys.*, 1935, 32, 455; *Proc. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1935, 8, 41. "Opacity" *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 311; 1937, 18, 388; *Current. Sci.*, 1936, 4, 870.

FIG. I.

Potassium molybdate.

It will be noticed in Fig. 1 that the viscosity corresponding to the first maximum is greater with mixtures containing larger quantities of potassium molybdate. This is due to the large number of micelles present in the gel-forming mixtures on account of the formation of greater quantity of thorium molybdate. Similar observations are made in curves in Fig. 2 and this may also be caused by an increase in the number of micelles. However, this behaviour of thorium ions in thorium molybdate gels is different from that in gels of thorium phosphate in which case these ions act as peptising agents and as such increase the degree of dispersity and the density of charge on the micelles and lower the rate of increase of viscosity. The difference in the two cases lies in the nature of the coagulating electrolyte; in the former it is potassium nitrate which gives a high concentration of nitrate ions and in the latter it is nitric acid which is comparatively less ionised. The abundance of the coagulating ions in thorium molybdate gels overcomes the peptising action of thorium ions.

FIG. 2.

Thorium nitrate.

FIG. 3.

Hydrochloric acid.

Hydrogen ions (Fig. 3) tend to increase the value of the first maximum abruptly as the concentration of HCl in the mixture is increased to 0.05*N* but this drops down when it is further increased to 0.06*N*. An increase in the rate of change of viscosity with increase in the concentration of the acid has also been observed in the case of thorium phosphate gels and is caused by the coagulating action of H^+ ions. Greater concentration of H^+ -ions act as peptising agents and cause a lowering in viscosity.

Effect of Electrolytes, Non-electrolytes and their Mixtures.

Electrolytes, non-electrolytes and mixtures of these are known to alter the viscosity of a colloidal system in the most varied manner (*vide*, Ostwald, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1913, 9, 34), Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 6, 641) found that the viscosity of a number of metallic hydroxide sols decreases on the addition of peptising electrolytes. Dhar and Chakravarty (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 225) found an irregular change in viscosity of silicic acid sols with increasing quantities of electrolytes. Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384) measured the viscosity of silicic acid gel-forming mixtures and found that there is an increase or decrease in the rate of change of viscosity on increasing the concentration of acetic

acid in alkaline or acidic mixtures. Mehta, Parmar and Prasad (*loc. cit.*) have studied the effect of the addition of acids and sodium chloride on the viscosity of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures and have found that they increase the rate of change of viscosity with time.

The effect of addition of non-electrolytes and of mixtures of non-electrolytes and electrolytes appears to have received special attention

of colloid chemists. Billitzer's work (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 48, 312) on a negatively charged platinum sol has shown that it can be discharged and charged positively by varying the amounts of alcohol. Levites (*Z. Chem. Ind. Kolloide*, 1908, 2, 237) found that non-electrolytes retard the sol-gel transformation of gelatine and agar-agar. Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 991) observed the accelerating effect of alcohols on the alkaline mixtures and a retarding effect on acidic ones. Mehta, Parmar and Prasad (*loc. cit.*) found that the rate of change of viscosity of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures decreases

as increasing amounts of the non-electrolytes are added to them.

In the present investigation the required quantities of the electrolytes, non-electrolytes and their mixtures were added to the mixture containing 0.24g. of thorium nitrate, 0.05g. of potassium molybdate and 0.04N-HCl. The results are shown graphically as follows :

Fig. 5. Effect of different volumes of 0.01N-KCl and K_2SO_4 .

Fig. 6. Effect of methyl, ethyl and propyl alcohols, glycerine, and 10 % solution of sucrose.

Fig. 7. Effect of methyl, ethyl and propyl alcohols, in the presence of KCl and K_2SO_4 .

It will be observed from these figures that the addition of electrolytes, non-electrolytes and their mixtures does not essentially alter the nature of the viscosity-time curves. A few observations made in each case are recorded below.

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

It will be noted in Fig. 5 that after the first fall in viscosity it rises continuously almost linearly in most cases, and the ultimate value reached is, in all cases, much greater than the first maximum value. This behaviour is different from that observed when no extra electrolytes are added to the gel forming mixtures. The added electrolytes hasten the rate of coagulation (this is supported by a comparison of the relative effect of the same amount of KCl and K_2SO_4 and thereby increase the rate of change of viscosity. It may happen that stiffer structures are formed under these conditions so that after the first break in the viscosity-time curves, the stiffness of the structure overcomes the stress involved in taking the viscosity reading. From the closeness of the various curves (not shown) it is concluded that the addition of increasing quantities of electrolytes does not magnify the nature of the effect to a large extent.

The effect of the addition of non-electrolytes shown in Fig. 6 is similar to that of the electrolytes, as in these cases also the viscosity increases to a value much greater than that corresponding to the first maximum. No remarkable change has been observed in the viscosity-time curves when

increasing quantities of the non-electrolytes are added to the gel-forming mixtures (curves not shown): the various curves are quite close to each other except with glycerine in which case they lie fairly apart. The only important observation that has been made is that while the viscosity value at the first maximum decreases as the quantity of ethyl and propyl alcohols and that of glycerine in the mixture is increased, it increases with the addition of methyl alcohol and sucrose solution. The peculiarity of alcohols is not surprising as they have been found to behave specifically under different circumstances but the behaviour of sucrose, which is a well known peptising agent, is certainly striking.

FIG. 7.

The effect of the addition of both electrolytes and non-electrolytes to the gel-forming mixtures is shown in Fig. 7. The presence of electrolytes hastens the coagulation of colloidal solutions in the gel-forming mixture and when non-electrolytes, some of which also behave in the same way, are added to the mixture, the rate of coagulation becomes very rapid

and stiffer gels may be formed. This is not clear from the curves (Fig. 7) which definitely show maxima.

Effect of Temperature.

The solubility of the disperse phase, the hydration of colloidal particles and the rate of coagulation of colloidal solutions undergo a change with a variation in the temperature at which they are measured. The process of gel-formation as suggested by various workers and by Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 8, 893, 991) consists of several stages and two of them are the formation of colloidal particles and an increase in their hydration. It will, therefore, be found that the entire course of gelation will be modified by a change in the temperature at which it is studied.

FIG. 8.

Viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures at different temperatures.
(9.05 g. Pot. molybdate).

Satya Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 193) found that in general the time of setting of inorganic jellies decreases as the temperature is raised with the exception of the jellies of thorium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide and mercuric sulphosalicylic acid which take a longer time to set at higher temperatures. Fleming (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 41, 427)

and Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 22, 516) found that the time of set of silicic acid gel forming mixture is increased with a slight increase in temperature, while Fells and Firth (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 243) reported that over the range of temperatures from 0° to 45°, the setting of silicic acid gels does not show a distinct variation with temperature. Szegvari and Schalek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 318; 33, 326) also observed that the time of setting of an iron oxide gel decreases with rise of temperature.

The viscosity measurements of dilute sol of albumin at different temperatures by Ostwald (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, 9, 34) showed that with rise of temperature it decreases at first in a normal manner, then increases and again decreases and the increase in viscosity takes place shortly before the appearance of turbidity. Ostwald has also given data on the viscosity measurements of a suspension of starch during heating wherein there is a normal decrease in viscosity in the beginning and then a sharp break followed by a regular increase.

The results obtained with thorium molybdate gels are shown graphically in Fig. 8 for mixtures containing 0.24 g. of thorium nitrate, 0.05 g. of potassium molybdate and 0.04N-HCl. It will be seen that the curves beyond the first maximum tend to smoothen as the temperature is raised. Also the value of the first maximum gets less with rise in temperature. This is in accordance with the view that the rise in temperature decreases the hydration of the gelling particles. The consequent decrease in the time of setting of these gels, determined by Fleming's method, with rise in temperature is shown in the following table .

TABLE II.

Temp.	Thorium nitrate = 0.24g HCl = 0.04N.				
	Pot. , molybdate → 0.03g.	0.04 g.	0.05 g.	0.06 g.	0.07 g.
35°	162'	87'	62'30"	42'0"	28'0"
40°	150'	85'	61'45"	39'30"	23'30"
45°	135'	65'	46'0 "	30'0"	15'0"
50°	120'	50'	34'15"	9'30"	6'15"